

Equivalents of generalized Brøndsted principle

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Abstract

In a short note in 1976, Brøndsted observed that certain fixed point theorems may be derived from theorems on the existence of maximal elements in partially ordered sets. In this paper, we apply his basic theorem and its various equivalent formulations. Consequently, all results in his paper are extended to several existence theorems on maximal elements, fixed points, stationary points, and common fixed points, common stationary points related to the Caristi fixed point theorem.

Keywords: Caristi fixed point theorem, preorder, metric space, fixed point, stationary point, maximal elements.

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1. Introduction

In a short note of Brøndsted [1] in 1976, he observed that certain fixed point theorems may be derived from theorems on the existence of maximal elements in partially ordered sets. Consequently, he obtained very useful three theorems including the Caristi fixed point theorem [2].

In 1982-2000, we had published several articles mainly related to the Caristi fixed point theorem, the Ekeland variational principle for approximate solutions of minimization problems, and their equivalent formulations with some applications; for example, see [3]–[8]. From the beginning of such study, we obtained a metatheorem for some equivalent statements on maximality, fixed points, stationary points, common fixed points, common stationary points, and others. We applied the metatheorem for various occasions. However, for a long period the metatheorem was not attracted any other one.

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Since 2022, we came back to the metatheorem, found its new version called the 2023 Metatheorem, and applied it to Ordered Fixed Point Theory with a large number of new results; see [9, 10, 11].

In the present article, as an application of the 2023 Metatheorem, we show that certain fixed point theorems are equivalent to theorems on the existence of maximal elements in partially ordered sets. In fact, those maximal elements are same to fixed points, stationary points, common fixed points, common stationary points, and others for certain types of maps or multimaps with nonempty values. Consequently, we improve and generalize all results of Brøndsted [1].

This paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we introduce the trivially true theorem (A) of Brøndsted [1] on partially ordered sets. A better form of (A) is called the Brøndsted principle. Section 3 devotes to introduce a particular form of the Metatheorem. As applications of the particular form, in Section 4, two theorems (B) and (C) in [1] are improved and equivalently formulated. Finally, Section 5 deals with some conclusion.

2. Birth of Brøndsted Principle

The main point in [1] is to show how certain fixed point theorems can be deduced from the following simple observation:

(A) *Let (E, \preceq) be a partially ordered set which admits at least one maximal element. Let $f : E \rightarrow E$ be a map such that $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in E$. Then f admits at least one fixed point.*

Brøndsted [1] noted: “Among the partially ordered sets having maximal elements we shall call attention to a certain type first considered by E. Bishop and R. R. Phelps. Let (E, d) be a metric space, and let φ be a real valued function on E . Define $\preceq_{d,\varphi}$ by letting $x \preceq_{d,\varphi} y$ if and only if $d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y)$. Then $\preceq_{d,\varphi}$ is a partial order, which admits at least one maximal element provided that (E, d) is complete and φ is lower semicontinuous and bounded below. Therefore, invoking also (A) we obtain” the Caristi-Kirk fixed point theorem.

Here we find why Brøndsted adopted partially ordered sets in (A) instead of preordered sets, that is, the ones satisfying reflexivity and transitivity. Moreover, we will see later that the maximal element in (A) is a fixed point of f .

Now we adopt the following new one instead of (A):

Brøndsted Principle. *Let (E, \preceq) be a preordered set and $f : E \rightarrow E$ be a map such that $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in E$. Then a maximal element $v \in E$ is a fixed point of f .*

Note that this is better than (A).

3. Extremal Element Principles

In this section, we give equivalent formulations of the Brøndsted principle by applying the 2023 Metatheorem [10, 11]. The Metatheorem guarantees the truth of all items when one of them is true. Since 1985, we have shown nearly one hundred cases of such situations; see the references at the end of this article.

As an application of Metatheorem, we apply it to preordered sets. A maximal or minimal element will be called an extremal element. From our 2023 Metatheorem, we deduced the following prototype of Extremal Element Principles for multimaps having *nonempty values*; see [10, 11]:

Theorem 3.1. *Let (X, \preceq) be a preordered set and A be a nonempty subset of X . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

(α) *There exists a maximal (resp. minimal) element $v \in A$ such that $v \not\preceq w$ (resp. $w \not\preceq v$) for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*

(β) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$), then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(γ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ (resp. $f(x) \preceq x$) for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(δ) Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$). Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ϵ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$) holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(η) If Y is a subset of X such that for each $x \in A \setminus Y$ there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq z$ (resp. $z \preceq x$), then there exists a $v \in A \cap Y$.

Remark 3.2. (1) Note that we claimed that (α)-(η) are equivalent in Theorem 3.1 and did not say that they are true. For a counter-example, consider the real line \mathbb{R} with the usual order. However, we gave many true examples based on the original sources; see the articles mentioned in our [9, 10, 11].

(2) All of the elements v 's in Theorem 3.1 are same as we have seen in the proof of Metatheorem; see [9, 10, 11].

(3) If \mathfrak{F} is a singleton, each of (β)-(ϵ) is denoted by ($\beta 1$)-($\epsilon 1$), respectively. They are also equivalent to (α)-(η); see [9, 10, 11].

(3) Theorem 3.1 improves the Abian-Brown fixed point theorem, the Tarski-Kantorovitch theorem, and Zorn's lemma; see [9].

(4) The 29 references of Park [6] show the origins, variants, consequences, and applications of early forms of Theorem 3.1, and we indicate only names of their authors: Banach (1922), Bishop-Phelps (1961), Phelps (1964), Abian (1971), Smithon (1971, 1973), Kasahara (1975), Caristi (1976), Höft-Höft (1976), Maschler-Peleg (1976), Ekeland (1979), Turinici (1980-1984), Tuy (1981), and others.

4. Equivalents of Brøndsted Principle

In this section, as examples of Theorem 3.1, the statements (B) and (C) of Brøndsted [1] are equivalently formulated.

Theorem 4.1. Let (X, d) be a complete metric space, and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ lower semicontinuous and bounded below. Define a partial order \preceq on X by

$$x \preceq y \text{ iff } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y).$$

Then the following equivalent statements hold:

(α) There exists a maximal element $v \in X$; that is, $d(v, w) > \varphi(v) - \varphi(w)$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.

(β) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying $d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(γ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ such that, for any $x \in X$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(δ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in X \setminus T(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v \in T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ϵ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that $d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y)$ holds for any $x \in X$ and any $y \in T(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in X$, that is, $\{v\} = T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(η) If Y is a subset of X such that, for each $x \in X \setminus Y$, there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $d(x, z) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(z)$, then there exists an element $v \in Y$.

Note that Theorem 4.1(β 1) is given in [1] as (B), which is the celebrated Caristi fixed point theorem, and others except (α) and (η) are its generalizations. Therefore Theorem 4.1(α)–(η) hold.

To illustrate how (A) may be used to establish other types of fixed point theorems, Brønsted [1] stated the following:

(C) Let F be a closed subset of a Banach space X , let $z \in X \setminus F$, and let $0 < r < \inf_{y \in F} \|z - y\|$. Let $T : F \rightarrow F$ be a map which maps each $x \in F$ in the direction of the closed ball $B(z, r)$, i.e. if $Tx \neq x$, then $x + t(Tx - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$. Then T has at least one fixed point.

In fact, define \preceq on F by letting

$$x \preceq y \text{ iff } x = y \text{ or } x + t(y - x) \in B(z, r) \text{ for some } t > 1.$$

Now by applying (C), we obtain the following:

Theorem 4.2. Let X be a closed subset of a Banach space E , let $z \in E \setminus X$, and $0 < r < \inf_{y \in X} \|z - y\|$.

Then the following equivalent statements hold:

(α) There exists a maximal element $v \in X$; that is, $v + t(w - v) \notin B(z, r)$ for any $t > 1$ and any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.

(β) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ such that for any $x \in X$, we have $x + t(f(x) - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(γ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in X$ with $x + t(f(x) - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(δ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that $x + t(y - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$ holds for any $x \in X$ and any $y \in T(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v \in T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ϵ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in X$ and any $y \in T(x) \setminus \{x\}$, we have $x + t(y - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in X$, that is, $\{v\} = T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(η) If Y is a subset of X such that, for each $x \in X \setminus Y$, there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x + t(z - x) \in B(z, r)$ for some $t > 1$, then there exists an element $v \in Y$.

Note that Theorem 4.2(γ 1) holds by (C). Therefore, all of equivalent (α)–(η) hold by Theorem 3.1.

5. Conclusion

We improved statements (A), (B), and (C) in [1] by Theorems 3.1, 4.1 and 4.2, respectively. Moreover, they have several equivalent formulations and the fixed points in them are actually same to certain maximal points, stationary points, collectively fixed points, collectively stationary points, and others. Therefore, if we have a theorem on any of such points, then we can deduce at least ten equivalent theorems on other types of points.

In many fields of mathematical sciences, there are plentiful number of theorems concerning maximal points or fixed points that can be applicable our Theorem 3.1. Some of such theorems can be seen in our previous works in [3]–[11]. Therefore, a metatheorem like Theorem 3.1 is a machine to find new equivalent theorems with simple proofs.

For more general theory including this study, see [9]. Our original manuscript of this paper was based on an old form of the 2023 Metatheorem.

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